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WP7 – ACCEPT demonstration activities

D7.10 – Demonstration activity report from the Swiss pilot site v1

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Table of Content

Project Consortium	4
Table of Content	5
Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms.....	6
List of Figures	7
List of Tables	8
1. Introduction	10
1.1. <i>Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable</i>	<i>10</i>
1.2. <i>Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables.....</i>	<i>10</i>
1.3. <i>Structure of the Deliverable</i>	<i>10</i>
2. Demonstration Plan	11
2.1. <i>Community objectives.....</i>	<i>12</i>
2.2. <i>Local Regulatory Framework and Constraints</i>	<i>13</i>
2.3. <i>Description of the Demonstration Plan.....</i>	<i>14</i>
3. Preparation of the Pilot Test-Bed	17
4. Support activities	19
5. Next steps	21
References	22

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Definition
AE	Acceptance & Engagement
AIC	Arena Innovation Community
BAM	Building Asset Manager
BC	Business Case
BIML	Building Information Management Layer
BU	Business-related
Dx.y	Deliverable x.y
DAM	District Asset Manager
DC	Direct Current
DER	Distributed Energy Resource
DIML	District Information Management Layer
DR	Demand Response
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EC	Energy Community
ER	Energy-related key performance indicator
ESCO	Energy Service Company
EV	Electric Vehicle
FLS	Fondazione La Sosta
HP	Heat Pump
I&C	Installation and Commissioning
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LEC	Local Energy Community
LV	Low Voltage
PV	Photovoltaic
SR	Data security & privacy / Reliability
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

List of Figures

Figure 1: Netatmo Smart Indoor Air Quality sensor (Netatmo, 2023)	19
Figure 2: Shelly 3EM 3-phase smart meter (Shelly, 2023)	20

List of Tables

Table 1: The use cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the key performance indicators.	12
Table 2: The business cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the key performance indicators.	12
Table 3: Relationship between use cases, community objectives, and assets.	13
Table 4: Steps to complete deployment	15
Table 5: Timeline for demonstration	15
Table 6: Testing approach for each use case	17

Executive Summary

This deliverable outlines the demonstration plan for the Swiss pilot site of the ACCEPT project, which aims to develop and test innovative energy solutions for local communities. The report provides an overview of the community's objectives, regulatory framework, and the plan for demonstrating the use cases (UCs).

The deliverable begins by summarizing the Swiss pilot site's assets and the modifications to the UCs that will be tested compared to D6.7. It then details the pilot test-bed for the Swiss pilot site designed to test the various use cases identified to be suitable. For each UC, the report outlines the relevant assets involved, the corresponding ACCEPT solution component, and the responsible technical partners.

Support activities will be provided to residents for installed sensors or meters in residential areas. This support will help residents understand how the equipment works and how to interpret the data provided by the sensors and meters.

Finally, the deliverable also outlines the next steps for each of the pilot sites. The next course of action involves completing the installation and commissioning phase, resolving any remaining issues, and beginning the demonstration phase following the timeline outlined in the report. The aim is to implement the UCs successfully and demonstrate the effectiveness of the ACCEPT solution for sustainable energy solutions in local communities.

Overall, this deliverable provides a comprehensive report of the first part of the demonstration activities for the Swiss pilot site of the ACCEPT project.

1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and Objectives of the Deliverable

This deliverable describes the work carried out under Task 7.4 up to month 26 of the ACCEPT project. This task aims to describe all the activities carried out for the demonstration of the ACCEPT solution at the Swiss pilot site.

The main objectives of the deliverable can be summarised as follows:

- Providing a description of the community objectives, regulatory framework, and constraints that affect the pilot site.
- Introducing the use cases to be tested at the Swiss pilot site and presenting the demonstration plan for validation activities.
- Preparing the test-bed for the ACCEPT solution operation and describing how the use cases will be implemented.
- Describing the support activities to ensure proper data collection and procedures to address any issues that may arise during the demonstration period.
- Outlining the actions planned to support and maintain engagement among the pilot participants.

This first version of the report covers the work performed from the start of the task, month 20, until month 26. The deliverable will be updated at month 33 and month 40 with results from the testing of the ACCEPT solution and associated impacts, including iterative improvements and optimizations.

1.2. Relation to other Tasks and Deliverables

The main interdependencies of this deliverable to tasks and deliverables of the same and other Work Packages (WP) can be summarized as:

- D2.1: Use and business cases to be tested in each pilot site are described thoroughly in this deliverable. The responsible technical partners for each Use Case (UC) are also indicated.
- D2.2: The Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and the datasheet for each KPI are detailed in this deliverable.
- D2.4: The system architecture description and a further description of the UCs is provided in this deliverable.
- D2.8: Report on innovative business models and service/contract design.
- D6.1: A more detailed description of the IoT infrastructure which is installed in the pilot sites.
- D6.6: A first introduction to the deployment of the ACCEPT system in a controlled environment is given in this deliverable.
- D6.7: This deliverable provides a detailed description of the validation scenarios which will be tested in the Swiss pilot site and is strongly connected to the demonstration activity report.
- T7.1: This task deals with consumer validation of service and content design.
- WP8: This work package assesses the impact of the ACCEPT solution on the demonstration sites and analyse the results of the demonstration activities to elaborate the business plan and define the exploitation.
- D9.10: This deliverable develops the replication roadmap and the plan for scaling-up of the solution based on the real pilot results.

The progress of this deliverable is crucial for the whole progress and success of D7.11 – Demonstration activity report from the Swiss pilot site v2.

1.3. Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable is structured as follows:

- Section 1 provides an overview of the scope, objectives, and interdependencies of the deliverable, as well as its structure.
- Section 2 describes the demonstration plan for the Swiss pilot site, including the community objectives, local regulatory framework, and changes to the use cases compared to D6.7.
- Section 3 covers the hardware and software deployment for the Swiss pilot site, including the installation of the IoT infrastructure, communication protocols, and data management systems.
- Section 4 details the support activities related to devices installed in the premises.
- Section 5 explains the next steps in the demonstration process.

2. Demonstration Plan

This section describes the demonstration plan for the Swiss pilot site, detailing the objectives of the community and how they link to the demonstration activities that will be carried out, the local regulatory framework, and the complete plan for the demonstration of the UCs. The section starts with a brief recap of the assets of the Swiss pilot site (refer to D6.7 for a more detailed description) and the changes in the UCs to be tested compared to D6.7.

RECAP OF THE PILOT SITE ASSETS

There are two pilot sites located in Switzerland: the Arena Innovation Community (AIC) and Fondazione La Sosta (FLS). These pilot sites offer different contexts for exploring demand response (DR) strategies and optimizing self-consumption with distributed energy resources (DERs). AIC is an Energy Community (EC) according to the Swiss law, while FLS is an assisted-living facility whose central heating system was upgraded in 2021 with the replacement of the gas boilers with Heat Pumps (HPs).

Two residential assets are included in the project. The first asset, AIC-AEM104, is a 3-apartment building where the consumption of an 11 kW_{th} heat pump will be monitored to evaluate "what-if" scenarios of demand response. The second asset, FLS-AEM125, is a 30-apartment building where the central heating HPs will be controlled by managing the secondary space heating pump.

Additionally, the project includes several district assets in the AIC. For example, the electric flexibility (hydraulic pump) of the district heating will be managed by varying the supply temperature of the distribution network. Another asset is the Electric Vehicle (EV) 11 kW DC charging station and the related car-sharing vehicle where optimal flexibility management will be tested by utilizing its bidirectional charging/discharging capabilities. This is an additional district level asset not originally included in the project, but its inclusion will add value to the project as it enables the testing of UC6 in the Swiss pilot site. Lastly, the district battery and PV plants will aim to improve self-consumption within the energy community. Unfortunately, the manufacturer of the district battery ceased operation in January 2023, thus the commissioning of the system was not completed and is not currently available. AEM understands the importance of this component and is dedicated to find a suitable replacement that can meet the needs of the community and project.

CHANGES TO THE USE CASES COMPARED TO D6.7

The updated version of the use cases for the Swiss pilot site of the ACCEPT project has been carefully reviewed to ensure that the testing process is comprehensive and effective. While a preliminary version of the use cases was available in D6.7, the relevant differences are explained below to provide a more detailed understanding of the changes.

UC2 (Virtual Energy Storage optimization) has been added to the testing plan after successful preliminary tests at the FLS-AEM125. This use case involves using the building's thermal inertia and hot water tanks to store energy for heating purposes. This addition to the testing plan is significant because it provides a unique opportunity to test the effectiveness of the ACCEPT solution in optimizing energy storage for heating purposes.

UC6 (Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification) can now be tested at the Arena Innovation Community thanks to the addition of a bidirectional EV charger in Q3-2022. This inclusion is particularly important because it allows testing of the ACCEPT solution's ability to manage smart charging and flexibility quantification for electric vehicles in one pilot site.

After careful review, it was decided not to test UC8 and UC9 at the Swiss pilot site. This decision was made jointly with the technical partners due to the lack of a dynamic tariff that limits the possibility for implicit and explicit demand response. This point is further highlighted in section 2.2 on the local regulatory framework. It is important to note that AIC-AEM104 will not be directly controlled but is included in the project for "what-if" demand response scenarios.

The decision to exclude certain use cases has been made after careful consideration and is intended to ensure that the testing process is focused and effective. These use cases, however, will be tested under the other available pilot sites at the Spanish, Greek and Dutch energy communities.

Table 1 displays the correlation between the tested KPIs and the UCs in the Swiss pilot site, whereas Table 2 illustrates the connection between the tested KPIs and the BCs in the Swiss pilot site.

Table 1: The use cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the key performance indicators.

ID	Name	Key performance indicators
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	SR-01, SR-02, SR-03
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	EC-03, ER-04, ER-08
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	ER-01, ER-02, ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, MR-02
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, MR-02
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, ER-08, MR-01
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	EC-03, ER-01, ER-02, ER-06
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	AE-01, AE-02, AE-04, AE-06, BU-01, BU-02, BU-03

Table 2: The business cases tested in the Swiss pilot site related to the key performance indicators.

ID	Name	Key performance indicators
BC2	Energy Community as an Energy Service Company (ESCO) offering energy management services	BU-02, BU-04, BU-05
BC4	Energy Community as a Retailer	EC-01, EC-02, EC-03
BC6	Heating-as-a-Service Provider	ER-03, ER-04, ER-05, ER-08, MR-01

2.1. Community objectives

The formation of an energy community in Switzerland aims to achieve several objectives that benefit the local community. One of the primary goals is to increase self-consumption of local PV electricity, which can lead to greater self-sufficiency and energy independence. By optimizing the use of locally generated renewable energy, the community can reduce its dependence on external sources of energy and decrease its carbon footprint, contributing to climate change mitigation efforts.

The Swiss pilot site is implementing a range of UCs that are intended to support the community's goals around DR and self-consumption. Each UC is tailored to address specific objectives and is linked to particular assets within the community. This information is summarized in Table 3, with each row containing the use case ID and name, the community objective and the assets related to the UC.

Table 3: Relationship between use cases, community objectives, and assets.

ID	Name	Objective	Assets
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	To collect data on energy consumption and production from the assets to enable the other use cases	All assets equipped with meters and sensors for data collection
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	To optimise the storage potential of the water tanks and building thermal inertia for demand flexibility	Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125 heating system
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	To forecast the energy demand from prosumers and adjust their consumption	Heating system in AIC-AEM104 and Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	To manage and optimise the use of PV electricity and controllable loads within the AIC district to meet energy demand and improve self-consumption	AIC district heating, AIC bidirectional EV charger, AIC district battery and PV plants
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification	To quantify the flexibility of the electric vehicle charging station to adjust charging based on predicted energy demand and availability	AIC bidirectional EV charger
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	To optimise the scheduling and operation of the district heating system to optimize the performance	AIC district heating
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	To improve self-consumption of PV electricity and reduce reliance on the grid	AIC district battery, PV plants and controllable loads Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125 PV plant and heating system
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	To engage with residents and local communities to promote energy efficiency and demand response acceptance	EC participants

2.2. Local Regulatory Framework and Constraints

The Swiss Energy Strategy (ES) 2050, which became effective on 1 January 2018, serves as a vital policy framework for Switzerland's transition to a low-carbon economy. It centres on three key pillars that focus on withdrawing from nuclear energy, decreasing energy consumption and emissions per capita, and advancing the use of renewable energy sources and energy efficiency. As part of this strategy, the concept of an Energy Community (EC) was introduced, which aims to foster collaboration between energy consumers and producers. To promote energy efficiency, smart meters must be rolled out by 2027, with each Distribution System Operator (DSO) required to cover 80% of its delivery points (Federal Department of the Environment, Transport, Energy and Communications (DETEC), 2023).

The EC, or self-consumption community, is a group of end consumers who come together to form a community with the objective of maximizing their self-sufficiency and self-consumption (SvizzeraEnergia, 2021; Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation, 2016; Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation, 2007). The EC must

meet certain requirements in order to achieve this objective. These requirements include electrical contiguity, physical contiguity, no usage of the public grid, installed DER capacity, and a tariff that is lower than the domestic protected market tariff. The requirements are explained below:

- Electrical contiguity: one of the requirements for an EC is electrical contiguity, which means that all the members must be connected under the same substation. This ensures that the community is physically connected and can easily share resources such as electricity.
- Physical contiguity: another requirement for an EC is physical contiguity, which means that all the members must be close together. However, this requirement was removed from January 2023 relaxing the regulation.
- No usage of the public grid: a key requirement for an EC is that self-generated and consumed electricity must not pass through the public grid. This means that the community must generate and consume its own electricity, without relying on the public grid. The self-produced electric energy is used directly within the EC in which it was generated, thus users can avoid paying taxes and network usage fees.
- Installed DER capacity: an EC must have an installed DER capacity that is greater than or equal to 10% of the total connected load of the community. This means that the community must have a significant amount of renewable energy resources such as solar panels, wind turbines, or hydroelectric power stations.
- EC Tariff: the tariff for an EC must be lower than the domestic protected market tariff. This ensures that the community is able to generate and consume its own electricity at a lower cost than the general public.
- Single point of measurement: after the creation of the community, end consumers jointly have a single point of measurement towards the network operator, which is treated as a single end consumer. This simplifies the process of measuring and monitoring the electricity consumption of the community.

These are strict regulations in place to protect the low voltage (LV) grid. This is important because the LV grid is vulnerable to fluctuations in voltage and power, which can cause problems for the community. However, there have not been any significant LV grid problems, as DSOs tend to overbuild the network to avoid constraints. The development of DR mechanisms as an alternative to network expansion is currently limited. The use of flexibility is not incentivized by the cost regulation system and the electricity grid is oversized consequently. With the revision of the Electricity Supply Act, network operators in Switzerland are obliged to consider flexibility as an alternative to network expansion (Federal Assembly of the Swiss Confederation, 2007).

In Switzerland, the regulatory framework currently limits the ability of energy communities to participate in demand response programs that involve the use of stationary batteries. Specifically, stationary batteries cannot be charged from grid electricity, and can only be charged from DERs. Moreover, there is a double taxation policy in place, which means that both the charge and recharge of batteries are subject to taxation (SvizzeraEnergia, 2018).

In summary, the major constraints posed by the current regulatory framework are:

- Strict EC requirements hamper the development of the communities and the inclusion of additional DERs and controllable loads.
- Lack of a dynamic tariff creates general unawareness towards demand response in the general population and limits the development of explicit control mechanisms.
- The prohibition of charging stationary batteries with the electricity from the public grid limits the possibility of EC.

The Swiss regulatory landscape presents several obstacles and limitations that may affect the objectives of the ACCEPT project. One of the primary limitations is the lack of a clear and supportive regulatory framework for energy communities. The current regulations do not provide sufficient incentives for citizens to participate in energy communities and may limit their ability to access the energy market. In terms of the ACCEPT project objectives, the lack of a clear regulatory framework may hinder the development of business models and services that enable the participation of residential communities in demand response markets/services. This limitation may also impact the ability of energy communities to offer value-adding services to customers and participate fully in the energy and flexibility markets. The participation of AEM in the ACCEPT project can contribute to the alleviation of regulatory constraints by providing insights and recommendations for regulatory reform. AEM's involvement in the project can also help to raise awareness and promote the benefits of energy communities among policymakers and other stakeholders.

Despite these regulatory limitations, the Swiss pilot site is still able to test a range of demand response and self-consumption strategies, utilizing the assets available. By having carefully selected the assets and use cases to be tested, the project aims to provide valuable insights within the current regulatory framework.

2.3. Description of the Demonstration Plan

As previously stated in D6.7, the preparation of the pilot site for demonstration has been delayed due to various reasons, mainly the complexity of the industrial system, and the involvement of third parties (refer to Table 4 for the steps to complete deployment). As a result, the initial demonstration activities are now expected to start in

June 2023, with the Installation and Commissioning (I&C) phase scheduled to be completed by August 2023. Full demonstration activities will take place during the next heating season in October 2023, but some assets are ready for demonstration activities earlier. However, with more than half a year available for testing, there is enough time available to conduct thorough testing of the use cases and business cases, and this will allow the project team to gather valuable insights and knowledge.

Table 5 shows the timeline for the demonstration of each use case at the Swiss pilot site. The estimated availability of related solutions and the dates for completion of installation and commissioning vary for each use case. As a result, the latter date is the bottleneck, and the demonstration can start only after this date. Moreover, certain UCs involve assets whose demonstration phase is dependent on the heating season, thus, the first available window starts in October 2023. It must be noted that the timeline provided in the table is provisional, and it will be updated in the following version of the deliverable.

Table 4: Steps to complete deployment

Asset	Steps to complete deployment
AIC-AEM104	Equipment to be procured. Equipment and Wi-Fi to be installed.
Heating system of FLS-AEM125	Minor issues to be resolved.
Multi-sensors at FLS-AEM125	Equipment to be procured. Equipment and central Wi-Fi to be installed.
AIC district heating	Further discussion with third party necessary. Equipment/software to be procured and installed.
AIC bidirectional EV charger	API for EV booking to be updated by third party. Internal API for control to be discussed.
AIC district battery	Internal company decision to be taken.

Table 5: Timeline for demonstration

ID	Name	Assets	ACCEPT solutions	Estimated availability of ACCEPT solutions	Estimated end of I&C	Estimated start of demonstration
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	All assets equipped with meters and sensors for data collection	BAM, BIML and Citizen-APP (QUE, CERTH)	March 2023 (M27)	May 2023 (M29)	June 2023 (M30)
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	FLS-AEM125 heating system	BAM and BIML (HYP, QUE)	March 2023 (M27)	April 2023 (M28)	October 2023 (M34) with the next heating season
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	Heating system in AIC-AEM104 and FLS-AEM125	BAM and BIML (HYP, QUE)	Available	May 2023 (M27)	June 2023 (M30)

ID	Name	Assets	ACCEPT solutions	Estimated availability of ACCEPT solutions	Estimated end of I&C	Estimated start of demonstration
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	AIC district heating, AIC bidirectional EV charger, AIC district battery and PV plants	DAM and DIML (CIRCE, HYP)	May 2023 (M27)	August 2023 (M32)	October 2023 (M34) with the next heating season
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification	AIC bidirectional EV charger	DAM and DIML (CERTH, HYP, CIRCE)	August 2023 (M32)	August 2023 (M32)	September 2023 (M33)
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	AIC district heating	DAM and DIML (CIRCE, CERTH)	August 2023 (M32)	August 2023 (M32)	October 2023 (M34) with the next heating season
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	AIC district battery, PV plants and controllable loads FLS-AEM125 PV plant and heating system	Energy community tools (HYP, CERTH, CIRCE)	May 2023 (M29)	May 2023 (M29)	June 2023 (M30)
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	EC participants	Surveys/workshops (SIN, UCC)	September 2023 (M33)	Completed	October 2023 (M34)

3. Preparation of the Pilot Test-Bed

This section summarises the preparation of the pilot test-bed for the Swiss pilot site. Table 6 provides an overview of the testing approach for each use case for the Swiss pilot site, outlining the assets involved, the relevant ACCEPT solution component, and the responsible technical partners. The use cases cover a range of scenarios, from metering and sensor energy data to active citizen and local energy community engagement. For each use case, the technical partners responsible for the implementation and testing of the solution are indicated in brackets. The testing approach for each use case varies, with some use cases focusing on monitoring and evaluating data accuracy, while others involve forecasting and optimizing energy demand and supply.

Table 6: Testing approach for each use case

ID	Name	Assets	ACCEPT solutions (responsible technical partners in brackets)	How the UC will be tested
UC1	Metering & Sensor Energy Data	All residential assets equipped with meters and sensors for data collection	BAM, BIML and Citizen-APP (QUE, CERTH)	The data will be monitored, and its accuracy evaluated.
UC2	Virtual Energy Storage optimisation	Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125 heating system	BAM and BIML (HYP, QUE)	The system will be monitored to model their consumption. The storage is exploited by managing the secondary space heating pump.
UC3	Consumer demand-side flexibility forecasting	Heating system in AIC-AEM104 and Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125	BAM AND BIML (HYP, QUE)	The assets will be monitored to identify patterns in energy usage and demand. The data will be analysed to forecast consumer demand-side flexibility, which will be used to optimize the energy system's overall performance.
UC5	Intra-day district-level DER flexibility management	AIC district heating, AIC bidirectional EV charger, AIC district battery and PV plants	DAM and DIML (CIRCE, HYP)	The district assets will be monitored in real-time, and their flexibility will be forecasted and optimized to balance energy demand and supply.
UC6	Day-ahead smart charging flexibility quantification	AIC bidirectional EV charger	DAM and DIML (CERTH, HYP, CIRCE)	The charger will be controlled to optimize its operation and charging capacity using advanced algorithms that considers the availability of the car-sharing <i>Honda e</i> vehicle
UC12	Optimal scheduling and operation of heating generation	AIC district heating	DAM and DIML (CIRCE, CERTH)	The system will be controlled by managing the hydraulic pump of the distribution network changing.
UC13	Increase self-consumption at local level	AIC district battery, PV plants and controllable loads	Energy community tools (HYP, CERTH, CIRCE)	The energy generated by the PV plants will be used to increase local self-consumption, and the

ID	Name	Assets	ACCEPT solutions (responsible technical partners in brackets)	How the UC will be tested
		Fondazione La Sosta-AEM125 PV plant and heating system		system's performance will be monitored to evaluate its effectiveness in increasing self-consumption.
UC14	Active Citizen and LEC Engagement	EC participants	Surveys/workshops (SIN, UCC)	The feedback of the participants will be collected through questionnaires, surveys or workshops.

4. Support activities

For the assets installed with sensors or meters in residential areas, support activities will be implemented to provide assistance to the residents if needed.

The majority of installations of sensors will occur at FLS-AEM125, where around 20 apartments will be equipped with the Netatmo Smart Indoor Air Quality Monitor that can be seen in Figure 1 (Netatmo, 2023). This sensor fits the requirements of the project and is compatible with AEM's data ingestion platform.

The rest of sensor installation will be performed at AIC-AEM104 to monitor the performance of the heat pump. The selected sensors are smart energy meters of the company Shelly. The Shelly 3EM (Shelly, 2023) is shown in Figure 2.

These sensors are off-the-shelf products with dedicated company support, which enables direct support for residential users. The device installation will be ensured by positioning and connecting it to a dedicated Wi-Fi network and users will be guided on how to use the device's app to monitor their indicators and interpret the data provided by the device. Technical support will be provided to users experiencing any issues with the device, including connectivity or malfunctioning sensors.

Furthermore, user education will be provided to improve understanding of how to interpret the data provided by the device. Overall, the support activities will enable residential users to effectively monitor the indoor air quality or the device performance and take informed action.

Regarding the district assets, the level of support requires a higher technical knowledge and expertise, thus the necessary support will be given with the help of AEM's IT partner when required. For example, in the case of FLS-AEM125, the partner is helping in the setup of a secure communication flow by aiding the technical partners that are setting up an additional virtual machine.

Figure 1: Netatmo Smart Indoor Air Quality sensor (Netatmo, 2023)

Figure 2: Shelly 3EM 3-phase smart meter (Shelly, 2023)

5. Next steps

The next steps are the completion of pilot site preparation in order to start the demonstration activities:

- AIC-AEM104 - residential heat pump: equipment and dedicated Wi-Fi system to be procured and installed.
- FLS-AEM125 – HP-based central heating system: minor issues with communication flow to be resolved.
- FLS-AEM125 – multi-sensors: best users to be identified, and equipment and dedicated Wi-Fi system to be procured and installed.
- AIC – district heating: communication system to be implemented, equipment to be procured and installed.
- AIC – bidirectional EV charger: third-party API to be completed, communication infrastructure to be updated.
- AIC – district battery: internal company decision to be taken.

When the I&C phase will be completed for each asset, the demonstration can begin according to the timeline presented in section 2.3. The advancement of the demonstration activities will be reported in D7.11 – demonstration activity report from the Swiss pilot site v2.

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